

REASONS OF POOR ACQUISITION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article states some challenges in gaining proper knowledge in foreign languages and explains several reasons for it. In this article some students are given as an example who find foreign languages difficult as a result of separate reasons.

Keywords: *acquisition, foreign languages, grammar, spelling, pronunciation.*

What is learning?

Learning is a process of acquiring knowledge in a proper field and it may include some tough steps.

Why is learning a foreign language considered as a difficult task?

If it is a language learning it may get more challenging. Because obtaining knowledge of a certain language means students should learn all of its aspects such as grammar, spelling, pronunciation and so on. That is why students, mostly new language learners confront more difficulties during the process.

The study of foreign languages is becoming a more important component of education worldwide. In addition to the fact that foreign language study is almost always obligatory for high school students, many elementary and middle schools now offer it as part of their curricula. Some school districts have established "magnet" schools for foreign languages, and they appear to be quite well-liked. Of

course, it goes without saying that it is far more typical for schools and universities to need foreign language studies in order to graduate. Foreign language education is, in fact, a pleasant and fulfilling experience for the student who is not hindered by a learning handicap. However, for a kid with a learning disability, it can be an incredibly stressful and humiliating experience, which is the exact opposite of what is intended.

Emotions are the heart of language learning and teaching, and yet they have largely remained in the shadows in the past decades of applied linguistic research. Swain (2013) argued, “emotions are the elephants in the room – poorly studied, poorly understood, seen as inferior to rational thought” (p. 195). The 21st century is the heyday of information technology. Our country's foreign economic and cultural ties are expanding, the social order of learning foreign languages is being formed, and the need to learn them is growing year by year. This fully applies to the preschool period. However, based on the researches and some of the data collected by several scholar and researchers reveal that it does not depend only preschool years but it mostly depends on the environment that surrounds you and the language learning atmosphere and people who you are interacting.

Psychologists and physiologists base the introduction of early foreign language teaching on children's natural propensity for languages and their emotional readiness to learn them. There is evidence in both locals and foreign psychology that a child learns a foreign language more easily than an adult. In this case, they are usually related to the sensitivity (sensitivity) of preschool and primary school age children to mastering common languages, in particular foreign languages. It is generally said that numerous people confront some problems in learning English as a second language in some non-English speaking countries, for instance in Lao People Democratic Republic (Lao PDR). According to research done to explore main reasons of students' weakness towards English language. A study focused on reasons that impact on poor performance of students of a college. This survey was conducted among 30 students and they gave at least 10 reasons for this. First most students stated that English teacher were not well prepared they

cannot provide learners with sufficient knowledge. Additionally, even they have acquired this language well they can teach students but cannot attract them with fascinating use of language. That is why majority of the learner's loose interest. Secondly, some students lack of background basic foundation of English language. Undoubtedly, it requires much time to obtain a knowledge in an appropriate sphere. Moreover, students do not have enough confidence to utilize a language that they have learned. It may result from the environment around them. If nobody uses that language, it gets more difficult to speak freely. Thus, many students are afraid of speaking English fluently and making mistakes. As a result, they get shy to use it among others. Their curriculum and syllabus are not done appreciate to learn English fully. Lastly, English language itself is a difficult one to learn because students are not well motivated and encouraged to gain it.

By doing some research with several undergraduate students who study other fields such as, economics, physics, biology (STEAM subjects/fields), I found out that these students also consider learning a foreign language as a challenging task to accomplish. They provided numerous reasons for this opinion. First of all, as they have their own studies, life problems and some of them work, they cannot devote enough time to learn another language. Because they have to deal with more significant jobs rather than learning a language. Additionally, people tend to focus on something that is more crucial and really necessary for their life. And learning a foreign language may seem to be a leisure time activity for some individuals. Furthermore, there may be another most important factor that makes learning process harder. It is the environment that surrounds us, such as language atmosphere in the place you are living. Sometimes people are curious about learning new languages and it seems and becomes an easy activity for them, but sometimes is vice versa. If people see and listen to people using the language that they are learning currently it may trigger them to study harder and better. Because it stimulates the feeling of proud to use this language and about its popularity among others. Alternatively, whether they cannot surround themselves with English speaking population, the learning process may get difficult and they may

lose motivation. Obviously, the main stimulation in learning is the passion and passionate students perform well in each field.

Comparing to the data that is shared, there are lots of factors can influence on acquisition of second or foreign languages poorly along with the teachers or the people who shares knowledge to young language learners. In some of the cases teachers are also a great factor to motivate students or attract students more and more to learn a new language. Additionally, sometimes not having enough knowledgeable teachers or trainer in some places can impact on the process of the acquiring a foreign language by students.

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